

An improvement on the Soboyejo and Nigerian Meteorological Agency Wind Isopleths Maps

L.O.Onundi¹, Philips Otuogba¹ and M.B. Oumarou²

¹Department of Civil and Water Resources Engineering, ²Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri

ABSTRACT

The paper reviewed the useful details of the Soboyejo Isopleths map for wind speeds and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency wind Documentation maps produced for Nigeria. The research work discovered some discrepancies in the interpretations given to the data produced by the Agency. Efforts were made to correct the wrong interpretations and a factor that varies from 7.86 to 11.67 was recommended to conveniently convert the daily mean produced by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency to the yearly mean produced by Soboyejo. Alternatively, the researchers decided to find a homogeneous mathematical relationship between, the Soboyejo's and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency results to produce results which correspond to 100 year mean recurrent interval. Finally, the results of the investigation were delightfully strengthened by the geographic description of meteorological stations in Nigeria. This has provided very useful information for the computation of altitude factors for various localities in the country.

KEYWORDS: Wind speed, Isopleths, Daily mean, Yearly mean, Geographical Locations

INTRODUCTION

Every nation has either developed or is in the process of developing its own codes of practice because its environmental conditions may be diverse and peculiar to such countries at different location of the World. It is a common practice for the Nigerian engineers to prefer to design or investigate all structures and facilities in accordance with the requirements of the British Standards even though we have Nigerian Standard Code of Practice, NSCP 1 (1973) for assessment of materials and general wind loadings. It is also true that most institutions in the country, teach their students, the fundamentals of the British Standards in different disciplines. While remarkable success have been recorded by using these standards for the design and investigation of various structures and other related facilities, it is also true that many diverse soils, materials and environmental conditions incorporated in the British Standards are Britain specific.

Therefore, to avoid a misleading result in our analytical and diagnostic procedures, an upgrade of the NSCP 1 (1973) may be required instead of a direct application of such recommendations and factors local to British conditions to Nigeria soils, materials and environmental conditions which are a lot different from what is obtainable in Britain. One important area of concern to the authors of this work is the appropriate prevailing wind speeds and the corresponding altitudes for the Nigerian environment.

Although, there are some common factors and coefficients that remain international and are conventionally accepted as such without much discrepancies and ambiguities; one such coefficient is Bernoulli international constant which is 0.5. The net pressure coefficient around the perimeter of buildings; which is generally acceptable to be 1.2 and many other examples which are acceptable any where in the World. The appropriate wind speed and their corresponding altitude are very vital for the design of our tall structures such as telecommunication masts, tall or multi-storey buildings, large span roof trusses and bridges to mention a few.

According to Auta and Maslennikov (2006), Nigeria and Russia have theirs namely NSCP 1 (1973) and SNiP (2004) respectively. Codes have generally been written since 1970 (Peter, 1978). A lot of researches are still on, in order to perfect these codes as deeper understanding grows about the response of structures to wind loadings. Some of these researches that have been carried out include but not limited to most international codes and standards listed in the works of (Kijewski and Kareem (1998), Kijewski *et al* (1999), Lee and Ng (1998) and Zhou *et al* (2002)). Recommendations from these studies are being adopted by major international codes and standards, with an aim to unify their application globally (Amin *et al* 1991). With this rising trend for the international codes and standards, some of the national codes are becoming unpopular (Auta and Maslennikov, 2006).

NSCP 1 has been written since 1973 and undergoing perfection, but cannot achieve this in isolation except the results are compared with other existing national and international codes and standards such as the Architectural

Figure 1 – Soboyejo Isopleths Map for Nigeria

Institute of Japan (1996), National Building Code of Canada (1995) and British Standard for loading for buildings - part 2: code of practice for wind loads BS 6399 (2004).

Estimation of Aerodynamic Wind Loadings, Recent Local and International Code Considerations

The first step that must be taken in order to effectively and efficiently carry out dynamic analysis and design of tall structures subjected to aerodynamic loadings; is to correctly assess the basic wind speed, V local to the site where the structure is to be built. This basic wind speed is usually obtained, through the results of the statistical analysis of the meteorological records of wind speeds known as the isopleths map for wind corresponding to various project locations or localities (i.e. including the local altitudes).

According to Asante (1988), to correctly assess this, the methods for the estimation of wind loadings are expressed in various codes of practice in terms of experimental, empirical and analytical approaches. The history of wind loads and its estimation goes back 400 years, when Newton estimates the resistance of a sphere in water and air by swinging at the end of a pendulum with the assumption that the decrease in oscillation amplitude is due to the fluid resistance. This led Newton to postulate the empirical relationship that:

$$\text{Wind load} = CV^2 \quad \dots\dots 1$$

where $C = 0.5$ or 0.613 or 0.625 is an empirical constant corresponding to different locations of the World and V the maximum sphere velocity in any swing. It is on this empirical relationship, that, the estimation of wind loads on the structure in general, is based today. The practice in the design of structures in general, is to design the structure to sustain, apart, from dead loads and or superimposed live loads, the loads that may be due to wind action on the structure. The design wind speed is generally based on the results of the statistical analysis of the meteorological records of wind speeds for geographical locations. This depends on many other factors local to individual countries, which will dictate the final value for use in the wind load estimates.

Until recently, some of the factors controlling the design wind speeds may be mentioned as: the topography, i.e. ground topology or roughness etc, terrain and size of the structure, the statistical considerations such as for how long the structure is to stand or serve its design purpose referred to as service life time.

A lot of research has been carried out on basic wind speed estimate using statistical analysis of extreme wind data in various parts of the world (Davenport (1960), Boyd and Kendali (1956), Gumbel (1954), Thom (1954), Jenkinson (1955), Whittingham, (1960), Sachs (1972), NSCP 1 (1973) and Fasanmi (1985)).

Examining the local situation in Nigeria, Okulaja (1968), carried out relevant studies of extreme wind data for Ikeja / Lagos wind gusts; while Williams (1970), carried out relevant studies involving the evaluation of 50-year data for Nigeria, as part of his estimation of wind loads on engineering structures in Nigeria. Soboyejo in 1971(Asante, 1988) using Gumbel Type I distribution of yearly highest gust for some meteorological stations in

Table 1 – Geographical Description of Meteorological Stations in Nigeria

S/N	STATION NAME	LAT.	LONG.	STATE	ELEV.
1	YELWA	10.53'N	04.45'E	KEBBI	244.0
2	BIRNI KEBBI	12.28'N	04.13'E	KEBBI	220.0
3	SOKOTO	13.01'N	05.15'E	SOKOTO	350.8
4	GUSAU	12.10'N	06.42'E	ZAMFARA	463.9
5	KADUNA	10.36'N	07.27'E	KADUNA	645.4
6	KATSINA	13.01'N	07.41'E	KATSINA	517.6
7	ZARIA	11.06'N	07.41'E	KADUNA	110.9
8	KANO	12.03'N	08.12'E	KANO	472.5
9	BAUCHI	10.17'N	09.49'E	BAUCHI	609.7
10	NGURU	12.53'N	10.28'E	YOBE	343.1
11	POTISKUM	11.42'N	11.02'E	BORNO	414.8
12	MAIDUGURI	11.51'N	13.05'E	BORNO	353.8
13	ILORIN	08.29'N	04.35'E	KWARA	307.4
14	SHAKI	08.40'N	03.23'E	OYO	
15	BIDA	09.06'N	06.01'E	NIGER	144.3
16	MINNA	09.37'N	06.32'E	NIGER	256.4
17	ABUJA	09.15'N	07.00'E	FCT	343.1
18	JOS	09.52'N	08.54'E	PLATEAU	1780.0
19	IBI	08.11'N	09.45'E	TARABA	110.7
20	YOLA	09.14'N	12.28'E	ADAMAWA	186.1
21	ISEYIN	07.58'N	03.36'E	OYO	330.0
22	IKEJA	06.35'N	03.20'E	LAGOS	39.4
23	OSHODI MET.AGRO	06.30'N	03.23'E	LAGOS	19.0
24	LAGOS (HQ) ROOF	06.27'N	03.24'E	LAGOS	14.0
25	LAGOS (MARINE)	06.26'N	03.25'E	LAGOS	2.0
26	IBADAN	07.26'N	03.54'E	OYO	227.2
27	IJEBU-ODE	06.50'N	03.56'E	OGUN	77.0
28	ABEOKUTA	07.10'N	03.20'E	OGUN	104.0
29	OSHOGBO	07.47'N	04.29'E	OSUN	302.0
30	ONDO	07.06'N	04.50'E	ONDO	287.3
31	BENIN	06.19'N	05.06'E	EDO	77.8
32	AKURE	07.17'N	05.18'E	ONDO	375.0
33	WARRI	05.31'N	05.44'E	DELTA	6.1
34	LOKOJA	07.47'N	06.44'E	KOGI	62.5
35	ONITSHA	06.09'N	06.47'E	ANAMBRA	67.0
36	PORT-HARCOURT	04.51'N	07.01'E	RIVERS	19.5
37	OWERRI	05.29'N	07.00'E	IMO	91.0
38	ENUGU	06.28'N	07.33'E	ENUGU	141.8
39	UYO	05.30'N	07.55'E	AKWA IBOM	38.0
40	CALABAR	04.58'N	08.21'E	CROSS RIVER	61.9
41	MAKURDI	07.44'N	08.32'E	BENUE	112.9
42	IKOM	05.58'N	08.42'E	CROSS RIVER	119.0
43	OGOJA	06.40'N	08.48'E	CROSS RIVER	117.0

Source: (NCC, 2009)

3. Methods

The information obtained from the NCC report on “Technical Specifications for the Installation of Telecommunications Mast and Towers” (Figure 2) and Soboyejo Isopleths map developed for Nigeria (Figure 1) were used as the basic data for this investigation and review. The Microsoft Excel was used as the main tool for the linear interpolations and extrapolations of data shown in Table 2. The corresponding graph and best fit equations of the scattered point-type for these basic data are as shown in Table 3 and Figure 3.

Table 2.0 - Soboyejo and Meteorological Agency Isopleths Data for Nigeria

S / N	Basic Data	
	MET. AGENCY (2000)	SOBOYEJO (1971)
	m/ sec	m/ sec
1	3	35.00
2	3.2	35.68
3	3.4	36.41
4	3.8	37.22
5	4	38.07
6	4.2	38.97
7	4.4	39.90
8	4.8	40.93
9	5	41.99
10	5.2	43.10
11	5.4	44.25
12	5.6	45.45
13	5.8	46.68
14	6	47.96
15	6.2	49.29
16	6.4	50.65
17	6.6	52.06
18	6.8	53.51
19	7	55.00
20	7.2	57.00

Source : NCC (2009)

Table 3- Fitting the Curves for Soboyejo and NIMET Isopleths of Nigeria Wind Speeds

S/N	Type	Equations	R ²
1	Linear	$y = 1.145x + 32.42$	0.987
2	Polynomial	$y = 0.024x^2 + 0.626x + 34.33$	0.999
3	Logarithmic	$y = 7.469\text{Ln } x + 28.64$	0.792
4	Exponential	$y = 33.55e^{0.025x}$	0.997
5	Power	$y = 330.58x^{0.171}$	0.835

Figure 3 - Nigerian Daily and Yearly Wind Speeds Isopleths

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The interpretation provided by the NCC report on “Technical Specifications for the Installation of Telecommunications Mast and Towers” (Figure 2) indicates that:

The highest recorded wind speed over a period of 20 years is 7 ms⁻¹; this translates to a mere 420 mhr⁻¹. However, wind gusts of the order of 55 km hr⁻¹ have been recorded infrequently. Since these data form our

worst case scenario, masts and towers in Nigeria shall be designed to withstand a minimum ground wind speed of 70 km hr⁻¹.

These interpretation statements leave room for a lot of questions. For example, the interval of daily data collection is not known apart from this, the following general observations can be made:

- i. A 7ms⁻¹ is equal to 25200mhr⁻¹ and not 420mhr⁻¹ as reported, if the conversion is to be correct. Perhaps, the Agency (NCC) meant to write 420mmin⁻¹
- ii. Similarly, a 7ms⁻¹ will give 25.2kmhr⁻¹. This wind speed is too low for the usual yearly mean used for civil engineering projects at 50, 75 or 100 year mean recurrent intervals.
- iii. It is because of these high level of inconsistencies observed with the NCC interpretations when compared with Figure 2, which made the Soboyejo isopleths map (Figure 1) to be the preferred isopleths map for wind in Nigeria for this investigation.
- iv. The elevations in Table 1 provided in the NIMET documentation are however very useful data for the computation of altitude factors for different locations in the country.
- v. If Figures 1 and 2 are compared:
 - a. The isopleths wind speeds at some locations are lower or higher in their values. Therefore, a factor that ranges from 7.86 to 11.67 (Table 2) was recommended to conveniently convert the daily mean to yearly mean.
 - b. Similarly, the best fit relationship of $y = 0.024x^2 + 0.626x + 34.33$ was obtained between, the Soboyejo's and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency results to produce Figure 3 which corresponds to 100 year mean recurrent interval.
- vi. These findings can serve as useful guide for Nigeria in her quest for the development or upgrade of the national code NSCP 1 (1973).

CONCLUSION

- i. A 7ms⁻¹ wind speed will give a value of 25200mhr⁻¹ and not 420mhr⁻¹ as reported by the NCC. Perhaps the Agency meant to write 420mmin⁻¹, if the conversion is to be correct.
- ii. Similarly, 7ms⁻¹ will give 25.2kmhr⁻¹ but this is too low for the usual yearly mean used for the design of civil engineering projects at 50, 75 or 100 year mean recurrent intervals.
- iii. The Soboyejo isopleths map is comparatively more consistent as the preferred isopleths map for wind in Nigeria for this investigation. Some vital relevant data produced by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency were however adopted to strengthen the records.
- iv. The altitudes or elevations in Table 1 are however very useful data for the country. The information contained in Figure 2 are however difficult to interpolate or extrapolate while determining the actual corresponding values of prevailing wind speeds for such locations.
- v. If Figures 1 and 2 are compared:
 - a. The isopleths wind speeds at some locations are either lower or higher in their values. Therefore, a factor range of 7.86 to 11.67 (Table 2) was recommended to conveniently convert the daily mean to yearly mean.
 - b. Similarly, the best fit relationship, of the polynomial type (i.e. $y = 0.024x^2 + 0.626x + 34.33$) was established between, the Soboyejo's and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency results to produce Figure 3 which corresponds to 100 year mean recurrent interval.

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Corresponding Author

L.O.Onundi

Department of Civil and Water Resources Engineering, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri

E- mail: onundii@yahoo.co.uk